

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Not excavated in 2011. Remains of later tufo floor visible at surface, evidence of earlier tufo floor visible in section provided by later drainage cut along eastern perimeter, Bordered on east, south, and west by walls of cut tufo blocks, on north by opus mixtum wall. Eastern wall appears to be set into soil, could indicate leveling of room 2, which has no visible slope. 3 western cuts and northern grave cut might show later activity in area. Rubble along eastern wall may relate to the wall itself. SU 1399 is intentional deposit above an earlier clay floor (SU 1462) large boulders near the wall help support this. It was deposited in order to raise the floor level and construct the tufo floor

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets): 0

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

charcoal

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Z. Fox, M. Moore

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